

Recompensation after TIPS reduces the incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma and increases survival in patients with cirrhosis

José Sánchez¹ | Sheila González¹ | Paloma Poyatos¹ | María Desamparados Escudero^{1,2} | Cristina Montón¹ | Juan-Antonio Carbonell³ | Elisabetta Casula⁴ | Jorge Guijarro⁴ | Paloma Lluch¹

¹Liver Unit, Digestive Disease Department, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Valencia, Valencia, Spain

²Medicine Department, University of Valencia, Valencia, Spain

³INCLIVA Biomedical Research Institute, Valencia, Spain

⁴Interventional radiology Department, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Valencia, Valencia, Spain

Correspondence

María Pilar Ballester, Liver Unit, Digestive Disease Department, Hospital Clínico Universitario de Valencia, Blasco Ibáñez, 17, Valencia 46010, Spain.
Email: mapibafe@gmail.com

Handling Editor: Dr. Alejandro Forner

Abstract

Background and Aims: It has been described that recompensation can improve prognosis in patients with cirrhosis. However, recompensation after transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) has not been studied. We evaluated the impact of recompensation after TIPS on the risk of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) and death, and we compared it with compensated cirrhosis patients.

Methods: An observational study of consecutive patients with cirrhosis undergoing TIPS between 2008 and 2022 was performed. Baveno VII definition of recompensation was used including patients with or without diuretics/Hepatic encephalopathy prophylaxis. A prospective cohort of consecutive compensated cirrhosis patients was used for comparison.

Results: Overall, 208 patients with cirrhosis were included, 92 compensated and 116 decompensated who underwent TIPS. After 1 year, 24% achieved recompensation. Liver function (MELD 12 ± 5 vs. 15 ± 6 ; $p = .049$), LDL-cholesterol (97 mg/dL vs. 76 mg/dL, $p = .018$), white cell count (7.96×10^9 /dL vs. 6.24×10^9 /dL, $p = .039$) and platelets (129×10^9 /dL vs. 101×10^9 /dL, $p = .039$) were associated with recompensation. Recompensation was associated with a reduction in the risk of HCC ($p = .020$). Multivariable analysis showed that this risk was significantly higher in non-recompensated patients ($p = .003$) but no differences were observed in recompensated compared with compensated patients ($p = .816$). Similarly, decompensated patients presented lower survival rates ($p = .011$), while no differences were observed between recompensated and compensated patients ($p = .677$).

Conclusions: Recompensation after TIPS has a clear impact on the incidence of HCC and death, with a similar prognosis than patients with compensated cirrhosis. Liver function is associated with recompensation, suggesting the importance of considering early TIPS in patients with indication.

KEYWORDS

cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma, recompensation, survival, transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt

Paloma Lluch and María Pilar Ballester shared senior authors.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2024 The Author(s). *Liver International* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, the natural history of cirrhosis has been seen as a unidirectional process, characterized by an irreversible progression from a compensated to a decompensated disease stage with a significant likelihood of developing further decompensating events and death.¹ However, a growing body of evidence indicates that the natural history of cirrhosis might not always follow a unidirectional pattern and there can be a partial regression of the structural and functional alterations of the liver following the removal of the underlying cause. This has led to the concept of hepatic recompensation, which was standardized during the Baveno VII conference.² Importantly, in a cohort of patients with alcohol-related cirrhosis 18% achieved recompensation, which was linked to a higher than 90% decrease in the risk of liver-related mortality.³ In case of patients with hepatitis B-related cirrhosis, 6% were recompensated after nucleot(s)ide treatment with similar results in terms of mortality.⁴ Recompensated patients seem to remain at risk for hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), but whether this risk is reduced after recompensation is unknown.³

Transjugular intrahepatic porto-systemic shunt (TIPS) procedure is an established therapeutic option to treat several portal hypertension-related complications including gastro-oesophageal variceal bleeding, refractory ascites and hepatic hydrothorax. In these cases, it has been shown to decrease the incidence of further decompensation and increase transplant-free survival compared to standard of care.⁵⁻⁷ Nonetheless, due to the diversion of portal venous flow, the risks of hepatic dysfunction and hepatic encephalopathy (HE) are increased.^{8,9} In the Baveno VII definition of recompensation, TIPS is not considered. Thus, whether a patient with cirrhosis undergoing TIPS can recompensate and which factors determine the probability of recompensation remain unknown. More importantly, the impact of recompensation on the risk of HCC and death in patients undergoing TIPS has not been studied.

Therefore, the primary aim of our study was to evaluate recompensation at 1 year after TIPS placement and its impact on the risk of HCC and death. Secondary aims were (i) to assess if the impact of recompensation at 6 months was similar to the one of recompensation at 1 year following TIPS on patient's prognosis, (ii) to define factors associated with recompensation at 1 year and 6 months and (iii) to evaluate whether recompensated patients with TIPS present similar prognosis than patients with compensated cirrhosis.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study design and patient selection

We performed an observational single centre study of consecutive patients with decompensated cirrhosis undergoing TIPS in the Hepatology Unit of the Clinic University Hospital of Valencia

Lay summary

In this study, we demonstrated for the first time that recompensation after TIPS in patients with decompensated cirrhosis reduces the incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma and increases survival with a similar prognosis than that of patients with compensated advanced chronic liver disease. Liver function is the main factor associated with recompensation. This highlights the importance of recompensation and suggests considering early TIPS in patients with portal hypertension-related decompensation to increase its likelihood.

between 2008 and 2022. Diagnosis of cirrhosis was based on liver histology or a combination of clinical, biochemical and imaging signs. Exclusion criteria were TIPS placed for non-cirrhotic portal hypertension, patients with cirrhosis treated with TIPS but without decompensation and/or HCC before TIPS. Only the first procedure was considered in patients who had multiple stents placed. Epidemiological, clinical and procedural data were prospectively registered while recompensation criteria was retrospectively evaluated from medical history records. Pre-TIPS evaluation and TIPS procedure are detailed in the Supplementary Material. Patients were followed-up until liver transplantation, death or study closure in 2023.

A prospective cohort of consecutive outpatients with compensated cirrhosis followed-up in the same Hepatology Unit was included for comparison. This cohort was created as part of the AMMON consortium to evaluate the role of plasma ammonia levels to predict liver-related decompensations and death in outpatients with cirrhosis. Parts of these data were previously published (PMID: 37277075).¹⁰ For this specific study inclusion criteria were age ≥ 18 years and cirrhosis based on liver histology or a combination of clinical, biochemical and imaging features. Exclusion criteria were history of liver-related decompensation, TIPS placement or HCC before evaluation. Similarly, patients were followed-up until liver transplantation, death or study closure in 2023.

2.2 | Recompensation assessment

The main outcomes of the study were recompensation after TIPS, development of HCC and death. Recompensation was evaluated at 6 and 12 months after TIPS placement and was defined as removal/suppression/cure of the primary aetiology of cirrhosis at any time before TIPS, resolution of ascites, HE (with or without diuretics/HE prophylaxis), absence of variceal haemorrhage and stable improvement of liver function tests. Stable improvement of liver function was considered as stability or improvement in the Child-Pugh score, which includes the three components of liver

synthetic function (albumin, INR and bilirubin), as long as ascites and HE were absent.

2.3 | Statistical analysis

Categorical variables were expressed as absolute frequencies and percentages (%). Distribution of the continuous variables was obtained by Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Normally distributed variables were presented with mean and standard deviation (SD), while non-normally distributed variables were described using median and interquartile range (IQR). Univariable analysis was performed to study baseline characteristics according to post-TIPS recompensation. Categorical data were compared with either chi-squared test or Fisher's exact test. Between-group comparison of quantitative variables was made with the *t*-test, Mann–Whitney *U*-test, one-way ANOVA or Kruskal–Wallis test, as required. Paired *T*-student was used for continuous variables with normal distribution and Related-samples Wilcoxon signed-rank test for continuous variables with non-normal distribution to compare biochemical parameters in patients who achieved recompensation at baseline and 1 year.

Cumulative incidence curves were constructed to evaluate time to HCC and transplant-free survival was studied using Kaplan–Meier curves from day of TIPS to date of censoring (loss of follow-up, liver transplant or study closure and HCC or death, respectively, whichever came first). Overall effect was studied using the log-rank test for mortality and Gray's test for development of HCC. Pairwise comparisons between groups were adjusted for multiplicity using the Benjamini–Hochberg (BH) method.

Univariable and multivariable Cox-regression analyses were performed to evaluate the independent contribution of recompensation on the risk of HCC and death. To evaluate whether risk of HCC in patients who achieved recompensation is similar to that of compensated patients, additional univariable and multivariable Cox-regression analyses were performed including compensated patients. Only covariates showing a clinical and statistical significance in univariable models, or participating as a confounding factor for the variable of interest, were included in the final stepwise multivariable models.

All tests were two-sided and a *p* value <.05 was considered statistically significant. Analysis was performed using SPSS Statistics (version 22) and R (version 4.0.2, R Core, 2021).

2.4 | Power calculation

A power calculation was performed for 1-year survival showing an achieved power of 0.999 using alpha error of .05, proportion difference of 100% and 44% and sample sizes of 28 and 88 in recompensated and non-recompensated groups, respectively. Analysis were two-sided and conducted with G*Power (version 3.1.9.7).

2.5 | Ethics

The study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethics Committee Board. Informed consent was obtained from each patient at the time of TIPS procedure.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | Study population and TIPS procedure

A total of 208 patients with cirrhosis were included, 92 compensated and 116 decompensated who underwent TIPS (Figure S1). Median age was 63 years old, and 75% of patients were males in both groups. Main aetiology of cirrhosis was alcohol (*n*=65, 56%) in decompensated patients and hepatitis C virus (*n*=40, 44%) in the compensated group. As expected, compensated patients presented lower Child-Pugh and MELD scores compared with decompensated patients (Child-Pugh 5 vs. 8, *p*<.001; MELD 8 vs. 13, *p*<.001). Baseline characteristics of the study cohort are summarized in Table 1.

A total of 28 (24%) patients were recompensated at 1 year and 31 (27%) at 6 months after TIPS placement. Most of the patients were males in both recompensated (*n*=19, 68%) and not recompensated (*n*=68, 77%) groups (*p*=.316) with a median age of 63 years (*p*=.905). The most frequent aetiology was alcohol-related cirrhosis in both groups. The main indication for TIPS was refractory ascites followed by variceal haemorrhage, with no differences between groups (*p*=.898). Baseline characteristics of recompensated and non-recompensated patients are shown in Table 2 and Table S1. More details about hemodynamic and clinical success as well as technical and shunt-derived complications are available in the Supplementary Material.

3.2 | Evolution after TIPS

Median follow-up of the study population after TIPS placement was 37 months (IQR 12–59). During the first-year post-TIPS, a total of 17 (19%) patients presented ascites, 20 (23%) HE, four (5%) variceal bleeding, 11 (13%) worsening of liver function, six (5%) were transplanted and 48 (41%) died, all in the non-recompensated group. In the recompensated or compensated groups, there were no events during the first year post-TIPS. Liver function and nutritional status were significantly better in recompensated compared with non-recompensated patients at 1-year post TIPS (Table S2). Patients who recompensated improved liver function (median Child Pugh score of 8, IQR 7–9, and 6, IQR 5–7, at baseline and 1-year post-TIPS, *p*<.001), hyponatraemia (median of sodium of 134 mEq/L, IQR 128–137 and 139 mEq/L, IQR 137–141, at baseline and 1-year post-TIPS, *p*<.001), cholesterol levels (mean HDL-cholesterol of 35, SD 17, and 58, SD 15, at baseline and 1-year post-TIPS, *p*<.001) and

TABLE 1 Baseline characteristics of the study population.

Variable	Decompensated (n = 116)	Compensated (n = 92)	p-value
Sex: male, n (%)	87 (75)	69 (75)	.169
Age (years), mean (SD)	63 (10)	63 (8)	.876
Aetiology, n (%)			
Alcohol	65 (56)	23 (25)	<.001
Hepatitis C virus	13 (11)	40 (44)	
MASLD	2 (2)	12 (13)	
Mixed	23 (20)	9 (10)	
Other	13 (11)	8 (9)	
Hypertension, n (%)	38 (33)	43 (47)	.034
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	47 (41)	35 (38)	.717
Dyslipidaemia, n (%)	20 (18)	40 (44)	<.001
MELD score, median (IQR)	13 (10–18)	8 (7–9)	<.001
CHILD-PUGH, median (IQR)	8 (7–9)	5 (5–6)	<.001
Biochemical, mean/median (SD/IQR)			
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.94 (0.7–1.4)	0.77 (0.7–1.0)	.007
Sodium (mEq/L)	135 (130–139)	140 (139–141)	<.001
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	121 (48)	169 (45)	<.001
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	73 (53–98)	106 (65–151)	<.001
Total protein (g/dL)	6.3 (5.4–7.0)	7.6 (7.1–7.8)	<.001
Albumin (g/dL)	3.2 (2.6–3.6)	4.2 (3.9–4.4)	<.001
Bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.4 (1.0–2.8)	0.8 (0.5–1.0)	<.001
AST (mg/dL)	42 (32–65)	32 (25–49)	.001
ALT (mg/dL)	26 (18–43)	28 (21–40)	.426
GGT (mg/dL)	70 (43–139)	55 (36–98)	.036
ALP (mg/dL)	146 (89–219)	81 (65–109)	<.001
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	9.6 (2.3)	13.7 (2.0)	<.001
Platelets (10 ⁹ /L)	103 (67–162)	127 (83–169)	.066
INR	1.3 (1.2–1.5)	1.1 (1.0–1.2)	<.001
Quick (%)	63 (19)	82 (18)	<.001

Note: Chi-squared test was used to compare categorical variables, T-student for continuous variables with normal distribution and Mann-Whitney U-test for continuous variables with non-normal distribution.

Abbreviations: ALP, alkaline phosphatase; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; GGT, gamma-glutamyl transferase; INR, international normalized ratio; IQR, interquartile range; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; SD, standard deviation.

inflammatory markers (mean leucocytes of 8×10^9 /dL, SD 5.8 and 6×10^9 /dL, SD 2.4, at baseline and 1-year post-TIPS, $p = .034$) over the first year (Table S3).

3.3 | Factors associated with recompensation

In non-recompensated patients, 48.3% had removal/suppression/cure of the primary aetiology of cirrhosis while all recompensated patients fulfilled this requirement as it was part of the definition of recompensation.

Liver function at the time of TIPS placement was associated with recompensation at 1 year, with lower MELD (12 ± 5 vs. 15 ± 6 ; $p = .049$; OR 1.09, 95% CI 1.05–1.12, $p < .001$) in recompensated patients (Table 2). Both MELD (12 ± 5 vs. 15 ± 6 , $p = .034$) and Child-Pugh scores (8, IQR 6–9 vs. 9, IQR 8–10, $p = .048$) were associated with recompensation at 6 months (Table S1). Similarly, biochemical parameters of the MELD and Child-Pugh scores were associated with recompensation at 1 year after TIPS placement, including lower creatinine levels ($p = .033$) and lower INR ($p = .040$). Other parameters associated with recompensation at 1 year were serum LDL-cholesterol levels ($p = .018$), white cell count ($p = .039$) and platelets

Variable	Recompensated (n = 28)	Non-recompensated (n = 88)	p-value
Sex: male, n (%)	19 (68)	68 (77)	.316
Age (years), mean (SD)	63 (10)	63 (11)	.905
Aetiology, n (%)			
Alcohol	23 (82)	41 (47)	.013
Hepatitis C virus	1 (4)	12 (14)	
MASLD	0 (0)	3 (3)	
Mixed	3 (11)	20 (23)	
Other	1 (4)	12 (14)	
Indication, n (%)			
Refractory ascites	16 (57)	43 (49)	.898
Variceal haemorrhage	10 (36)	37 (42)	
Other	2 (7)	8 (9)	
Hypertension, n (%)	5 (18)	33 (38)	.054
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	9 (32)	38 (43)	.300
Dyslipidaemia, n (%)	6 (21)	14 (16)	.534
MELD score, mean (SD)	12 (5)	15 (6)	.049
CHILD-PUGH score, median (IQR)	8 (7–9)	9 (8–10)	.078
TIPS placed in first decompensation, n (%)	4 (14)	15 (17)	1.000
Pre-TIPS HVPG, mean (SD)	20 (5)	20 (4)	.896
Post-TIPS HVPG, mean (SD)	8 (2)	8 (2)	.885
HVPG variation, mean (SD)	12 (5)	12 (4)	.811
Hemodynamic success, n (%)	25 (96)	70 (97)	1.000
Clinical success, n (%)	28 (100)	77 (88)	.063
Technical complication, n (%)	0 (0)	2 (2)	1.000
Shunt complication, n (%)	3 (11)	22 (25)	.109
Biochemical, mean/median (SD/IQR)			
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.8 (0.6–1.2)	1 (0.7–1.5)	.033
Sodium (mEq/L)	134 (128–137)	136 (131–139)	.095
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	139 (61)	115 (41)	.065
HDL-C (mg/dL)	35 (17)	34 (15)	.755
LDL-C (mg/dL)	97 (42)	76 (36)	.018
Triglycerides (mg/dL)	85 (51)	81 (41)	.688
Total protein (g/dL)	6.3 (1.3)	6.0 (1.3)	.321
Albumin (g/dL)	3.3 (0.7)	3.1 (0.6)	.225
Bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.1 (0.8–1.9)	1.7 (1.0–3.0)	.520
AST (mg/dL)	39 (31–56)	44 (33–75)	.333
ALT (mg/dL)	23 (17–43)	29 (18–43)	.330
GGT (mg/dL)	70 (43–356)	70 (43–135)	.497
ALP (mg/dL)	162 (94–284)	132 (85–212)	.280
Leucocytes (10 ⁹ /dL)	8.0 (5.8)	6.2 (2.9)	.039
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	9.9 (2.9)	9.5 (2.1)	.454
Platelets (10 ⁹ /L)	129 (78–227)	101 (59–140)	.039
INR	1.2 (1.2–1.4)	1.3 (1.2–1.5)	.040
Quick (%)	68 (19)	61 (19)	.093

TABLE 2 Baseline characteristics of decompensated patients undergoing TIPS according to recompensation at 1-year post-TIPS.

Note: Chi-squared test was used to compare categorical variables, T-student for continuous variables with normal distribution and Mann-Whitney U-test for continuous variables with non-normal distribution.

Abbreviations: ALP, alkaline phosphatase; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; GGT, gamma-glutamyl transferase; INR, international normalized ratio; IQR, interquartile range; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; SD, standard deviation.

($p = .039$; Table 2). Creatinine, LDL-cholesterol and white cell count were also associated with recompensation 6 months after TIPS (Table S1).

3.4 | Impact of recompensation on the risk of HCC

Cumulative incidence of HCC at 1, 3 and 5 years was 4%, 9% and 14%, and 19%, 32% and 38% in recompensated and non-recompensated patients, respectively, with significant differences between groups (Gray's test $p = .014$). Similarly, recompensation after TIPS was associated with a significant reduction in the risk of HCC compared with non-recompensation in both univariable (HR: 0.17, 95% CI: 0.04–0.78, $p = .023$) and multivariable analyses (HR: 0.11, 95% CI: 0.02–0.71, $p = .020$) including other factors such as age, sex, aetiology of cirrhosis, comorbidities or indication for TIPS (Table S4).

Cumulative incidence of HCC at 1, 3 and 5 years in the compensated group was 2%, 6% and 16%, without significant differences between recompensated and compensated patients (BH adjusted Gray's test $p = .84$; Figure 1). Multivariable analysis including compensated patients showed that risk of HCC was significantly higher in non-recompensated patients (HR: 4.44, 95% CI: 1.66–11.90,

$p = .003$) but no differences were observed between recompensated and compensated groups (HR: 0.83, 95% CI: 0.17–4.02, $p = .816$; Table 3).

Recompensation at 6 months showed similar results with a lower incidence of HCC compared with non-recompensated patients (BH adjusted Gray's test $p < .001$; Figure S2).

3.5 | Impact of recompensation on the risk of death

Survival was 100%, 88% and 76% at 1, 3 and 5 years follow-up in recompensated patients, and 44%, 35% and 24% in decompensated patients, with significant differences between groups (log-rank $p < .001$). Again, recompensation after TIPS was associated with a significant reduction in the risk of death compared with non-recompensation in both univariable (HR: 0.32, 95% CI: 0.16–0.62, $p = .001$) and multivariable analyses (HR: 0.34, 95% CI: 0.16–0.71, $p = .004$) including other factors such as age, sex, aetiology of cirrhosis, comorbidities or indication for TIPS (Table S5).

In patients with compensated cirrhosis, survival was 99%, 95% and 83% at 1, 3 and 5 year follow-up without differences when

FIGURE 1 Cumulative incidence of HCC in compensated, recompensated and non-recompensated patients at 1-year follow-up. Overall effect was compared using Gray's test.

Variable	Univariable		Multivariable	
	HR (95 CI)	p-value	HR (95 CI)	p-value
Sex: male	2.01 (0.59–6.85)	.267	2.73 (0.74–10.07)	.133
Age (years)	1.08 (1.03–1.13)	.002	1.08 (1.02–1.13)	.003
Aetiology				
Alcohol	Ref	Ref		
Hepatitis C virus	1.37 (0.44–4.25)	.585		
MASLD	1.55 (0.31–7.71)	.590		
Mixed	1.62 (0.40–6.49)	.499		
Other	2.83 (0.71–11.36)	.142		
Hypertension	1.89 (0.77–4.63)	.164		
Diabetes Mellitus	1.32 (0.55–3.20)	.533		
Dyslipidaemia	0.59 (0.21–1.61)	.301		
Biochemical				
Creatinine (mg/dL)	1.45 (0.65–3.22)	.365		
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	1.00 (0.99–1.01)	.930		
LDL-C (mg/dL)	0.99 (0.98–1.01)	.421		
Albumin (g/dL)	0.70 (0.40–1.22)	.212		
Bilirubin (mg/dL)	0.89 (0.53–1.49)	.658		
Leucocytes (10 ⁹ /dL)	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	.591		
Platelets (10 ⁹ /L)	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	.041	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	.032
INR	1.04 (0.43–2.53)	.922		
Quick (%)	1.00 (0.98–1.02)	.753		
Group of study				
Compensated	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Decompensated	4.54 (1.74–11.81)	.002	4.44 (1.66–11.90)	.003
Recompensated	0.72 (0.15–3.45)	.677	0.83 (0.17–4.02)	.816

Abbreviations: 95 CI, 95% confidence interval; HR, hazard ratio; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease; INR, international normalized ratio.

compared with recompensated patients (BH adjusted log-rank $p = .410$; [Figure 2](#)). Similarly, multivariable analysis including compensated patients showed no differences in time to death when compared with recompensated patients (HR: 0.79, 95%CI: 0.27–2.35, $p = .677$). Other factors associated with the risk of death were age ($p = .007$), creatinine ($p = .037$), bilirubin ($p = .002$) and cholesterol levels ($p = .014$; [Table 4](#)).

Recompensation at 6 months showed similar finding with a longer transplant-free survival (BH adjusted log-rank $p < .001$; [Figure S3](#)).

4 | DISCUSSION

The present observational study addresses the prognostic value of recompensation in patients with decompensated cirrhosis undergoing TIPS. The main finding of the study is that achieving recompensation after TIPS placement decreases the risk of HCC and mortality in patients with decompensated cirrhosis and equals that of compensated patients.

TABLE 3 Univariable and multivariable Cox-regression analysis for the risk of HCC development including decompensated and compensated patients.

As it is well known, decompensated cirrhosis is characterized by the development of liver-related complications that may progress to extrahepatic organ failures and acute-on-chronic liver failure with high mortality rates.¹¹ Portal hypertension is a consequence of cirrhosis and an important determinant of its disease course and prognosis.¹² Consequently, hepatic recompensation and disease stabilization are presumably accompanied by an amelioration of portal hypertension.¹³ The TIPS procedure is currently the only effective and fast option for lowering portal venous pressure that results in an improvement in the extrahepatic hemodynamic circulation.⁸

Baveno VII established specific criteria to define recompensation. Nonetheless, Baveno VII did not consider improvement of portal hypertension with TIPS and whether those patients can present regressive disease and achieve recompensation has not been studied. Attending the general criteria of recompensation, our study demonstrates that 24% of patients ($n = 28/116$) achieve recompensation after TIPS placement. This is similar to a recent study that showed that, after TIPS, nearly one-third of individuals reach recompensation.¹⁴

FIGURE 2 Transplant-free survival in compensated, recompensated and non-recompensated patients at 1-year follow-up. Overall effect was compared using log-rank test.

Although management of the primary aetiology seems to be crucial, it is not the only parameter that determines the probability of recompensation, as demonstrated by our study where almost half of the non-recompensated patients presented removal, suppression or cure of the primary aetiology. The role of MELD as a predictor of recompensation has been supported by multiple studies. Lower MELD scores at the time of listing for transplantation increase the likelihood of recompensation, whereas higher MELD scores seem to have a negative predictive effect on patients with hepatitis C or alcohol-related cirrhosis. These data suggest that there is a critical point beyond which decompensation may no longer reverse, even with the cessation of liver damage.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ However, MELD has never been established as a predictor of recompensation after TIPS placement, which highlights the importance of considering earlier TIPS placement in patients with an indication before reaching the aforementioned critical point.

Another factor that seems to influence recompensation in previous studies is platelet count.^{15,16} The present study confirmed that a higher platelet count is associated with recompensation after 1-year follow-up, although no association was observed with portal venous pressure gradient prior TIPS placement.

Serum cholesterol has been reported as an independent predictor of transplant-free survival in patients with cirrhosis undergoing TIPS.¹⁸ Consistent with this, we observed that serum cholesterol

and LDL-cholesterol levels are associated with recompensation, underscoring the importance of maintaining adequate cardiovascular and nutritional management before TIPS placement.

The question of whether recompensation correlates with a decreased risk of HCC holds significant importance in daily clinical practice. Regarding the effect of abstinence in alcohol-related cirrhosis, Rodriguez et al.¹⁹ demonstrated that abstinence reduced the risk of HCC, but only in those without a history of decompensated disease. Later, Hofer et al.³ showed that despite a trend towards a decreased incidence in recompensated patients, patients still remain at risk for HCC development. In patients with decompensated hepatitis C virus-associated cirrhosis, previous studies failed to demonstrate a significantly reduced risk of developing HCC following direct action antiviral therapy.^{20,21} Similar results were seen in patients with decompensated hepatitis B virus-related cirrhosis treated with antiviral therapy and subsequent viral suppression.²² However, Zhang et al.²³ recently demonstrated that achieving recompensation reduces the incidence of HCC in patients with hepatitis B virus who remain at a comparable risk to compensated patients with cirrhosis. Similarly, our study demonstrates that the risk of developing HCC in patients with TIPS who achieve recompensation is reduced compared with patients that remain decompensated, and that this lower risk is comparable to that of compensated patients, even when considering

Variable	Univariable		Multivariable	
	HR (95 CI)	p-value	HR (95CI)	p-value
Sex: male	1.61 (0.88–2.96)	.126		
Age (years)	1.02 (0.99–1.04)	.257	1.04 (1.01–1.08)	.007
Aetiology				
Alcohol	Ref	Ref		
Hepatitis C virus	0.71 (0.38–1.35)	.297		
MASLD	0.19 (0.03–1.39)	.102		
Mixed	1.38 (0.74–2.58)	.306		
Other	1.08 (0.47–2.46)	.854		
Hypertension	0.82 (0.50–1.34)	.429	0.66 (0.37–1.18)	.160
Diabetes mellitus	1.32 (0.81–2.14)	.268		
Dyslipidaemia	0.64 (0.36–1.15)	.134		
Biochemical				
Creatinine (mg/dL)	2.01 (1.47–2.74)	<.001	1.51 (1.02–2.24)	.037
Cholesterol (mg/dL)	0.99 (0.98–0.99)	<.001	0.99 (0.99–1.00)	.014
LDL-C (mg/dL)	0.99 (0.98–0.99)	<.001		
Albumin (g/dL)	0.53 (0.39–0.71)	<.001	0.68 (0.45–1.03)	.066
Bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.24 (1.15–1.33)	<.001	1.18 (1.06–1.31)	.002
Leucocytes (10 ⁹ /dL)	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	.019		
Platelets (10 ⁹ /L)	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	.081		
INR	1.27 (0.91–1.78)	.164		
Quick (%)	0.98 (0.97–0.99)	.003		
Group of study				
Compensated	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Decompensated	7.72 (3.76–15.84)	<.001	3.06 (1.29–7.23)	.011
Recompensated	2.33 (0.95–5.72)	.065	0.79 (0.27–2.35)	.677

Abbreviations: 95 CI, 95% confidence interval; HR, hazard ratio; INR, international normalized ratio; MASLD, metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease.

other factors such as comorbidities, aetiology of cirrhosis or liver function. This result underscores the importance of achieving recompensation in patients with cirrhosis but also emphasizes the need for HCC screening even after recompensation has been attained.

Regarding other clinical implications of recompensation, initial observations from prior research suggest a significant decrease in the risk of death. Hofer et al.³ observed a 91% decrease in the risk of liver-related mortality as well as a 78% decrease for all-cause mortality upon recompensation in patients with alcohol-related cirrhosis. These findings were also confirmed in hepatitis B virus-related cirrhosis recompensated patients after complete viral suppression. In addition, Hui et al.⁴ showed that there was not statistically significant difference in transplant-free survival between the recompensated and compensated patients. Several studies have confirmed that TIPS provides significant survival benefits over traditional first line treatment in selected patients.^{24,25} The results of the present study demonstrate that recompensation after TIPS not only improves survival but also equals that of compensated patients, even

when including other factors widely known to influence survival in patients with cirrhosis.

Importantly, the impact of recompensation on the patients' prognosis was not only seen in patients achieving recompensation after 1 year but also after 6 months of TIPS placement. This questions whether the current Baveno VII definition has to be revised according to real-world data.

The results of this study should be interpreted considering its strengths and limitations. One limitation is inherent to its observational methodology, which tends towards information bias and confounding variables. We attempted to minimize this by carefully reviewing medical records and performing multivariable analyses including potentially confounding variables. Another aspect to consider is that although the number of recompensated patients is small, power calculation demonstrated that the sample size is sufficient to address the hypothesis. Furthermore, the study includes a real-life well-characterized patient cohort, increasing the reproducibility of the results in the real world. The main strength of our study is that, while numerous articles only analysed factors associated with

TABLE 4 Univariable and multivariable Cox-regression analysis for the risk of death including decompensated and compensated patients.

recompensation, this is the first study to address the risk of HCC and survival after recompensation in patients undergoing TIPS and compared it with compensated patients of similar age and sex. Nonetheless, to evaluate the impact of recompensation for specific indications of TIPS, a multicentre study with larger sample size would be needed.

To sum up, recompensation at 6 months and 1 year after TIPS has a clear impact on patients with decompensated cirrhosis by reducing incidence of HCC and increasing survival, with a similar prognosis than that of patients with compensated advanced chronic liver disease. Liver function is the main factor associated with recompensation, together with other parameters such as creatinine, platelets, white cell count and LDL-cholesterol levels. Therefore, the results of this study highlight the importance of recompensation in patients undergoing TIPS and may be applied in clinical practice by considering early TIPS placement for managing several portal hypertension-related decompensations as a strategy to increase the likelihood of recompensation and improve patients' prognosis.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Statistical analyses were performed by JS, MBP, JAC. The manuscript was prepared and written by JS and MPB. SG, PP, MDE, CM and PL contributed to data collection and patient selection. EC and JG contributed to providing treatment to the patients. All authors have reviewed and approved the final submitted manuscript.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

To all the patients and members of the Hepatology and Interventional Radiology Unit of Hospital Clínico Universitario de Valencia, who contribute to advance knowledge.

FUNDING INFORMATION

MPB is supported by a Juan Rodés contract (JR23/00029), Instituto de Salud Carlos III. No funders were involved in study design, data collection, analysis, decision to publish or preparation of the manuscript.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All the data collected for the study are shown in the manuscript.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND PATIENT CONSENT STATEMENTS

The study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethics Committee Board. Inform consent was obtained from each patient at the time of TIPS procedure.

ORCID

Paloma Lluch <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3192-3820>

María Pilar Ballester <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7177-5696>

REFERENCES

1. D'Amico G, Morabito A, D'Amico M, et al. Clinical states of cirrhosis and competing risks. *J Hepatol.* 2018;68:563-576.
2. de Franchis R, Bosch J, Garcia-Tsao G, et al. Baveno VII—renewing consensus in portal hypertension. *J Hepatol.* 2022;76:959-974.
3. Hofer BS, Simbrunner B, Hartl L, et al. Hepatic recompensation according to Baveno VII criteria is linked to a significant survival benefit in decompensated alcohol-related cirrhosis. *Liver Int.* 2023;43(10):2220-2231.
4. Hui VWK, Wong GLH, Wong VWS, et al. Baveno VII criteria for recompensation predict transplant-free survival in patients with hepatitis B-related decompensated cirrhosis. *JHEP Rep.* 2023;5(9):100814.
5. Angeli P, Bernardi M, Villanueva C, et al. EASL Clinical Practice Guidelines for the management of patients with decompensated cirrhosis. *J Hepatol.* 2018;69(2):406-460.
6. Bureau C, Thabut D, Oberti F, et al. Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunts with covered stents increase transplant-free survival of patients with cirrhosis and recurrent ascites. *Gastroenterology.* 2017;152(1):157-163.
7. Larrue H, D'Amico G, Olivas P, et al. TIPS prevents further decompensation and improves survival in patients with cirrhosis and portal hypertension in an individual patient data meta-analysis. *J Hepatol.* 2023;79(3):692-703.
8. Strunk H, Marinova M. Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS): pathophysiologic basics, actual indications and results with review of the literature. *RöFo.* 2018;190:701-711. <http://www.thieme-connect.de/DOI/DOI?10.1055/a-0628-7347>.
9. Rössle M. TIPS: 25 years later. *J Hepatol.* 2013;59(5):1081-1093.
10. Ballester MP, Tranah TH, Balcar L, et al. Development and validation of the AMMON-OHE model to predict risk of overt hepatic encephalopathy occurrence in outpatients with cirrhosis. *J Hepatol.* 2023;79(4):967-976. Erratum in: *J Hepatol.* 2023 Dec;79(6):1571.
11. Engelmann C, Clària J, Szabo G, Bosch J, Bernardi M. Pathophysiology of decompensated cirrhosis: portal hypertension, circulatory dysfunction, inflammation, metabolism and mitochondrial dysfunction. *J Hepatol.* 2021;75(Suppl 1):S49-S66.
12. D'Amico G, Garcia-Tsao G, Pagliaro L. Natural history and prognostic indicators of survival in cirrhosis: a systematic review of 118 studies. *J Hepatol.* 2006;44(1):217-231.
13. Reiberger T, Hofer BS. The Baveno VII concept of cirrhosis recompensation. *Dig Liver Dis.* 2023;55(4):431-441.
14. Gao L, Li MB, Li JY, Liu Y, Ren C, Feng DP. Impressive recompensation in transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt-treated individuals with complications of decompensated cirrhosis based on Baveno VII criteria. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2023;29(38):5383-5394.
15. Pose E, Torrents A, Reverter E, et al. A notable proportion of liver transplant candidates with alcohol-related cirrhosis can be delisted because of clinical improvement. *J Hepatol.* 2021;75(2):275-283.
16. Aravinthan AD, Barbas AS, Doyle AC, et al. Characteristics of liver transplant candidates delisted following recompensation and predictors of such delisting in alcohol-related liver disease: a case-control study. *Transpl Int.* 2017;30(11):1140-1149.
17. Belli LS, Berenguer M, Cortesi PA, et al. Delisting of liver transplant candidates with chronic hepatitis C after viral eradication: a European study. *J Hepatol.* 2016;65(3):524-531.
18. Ballester MP, Lluch P, Tosca J, et al. Serum cholesterol predicts transplant-free survival in cirrhotic patients undergoing transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt. *Dig Liver Dis.* 2021;53(12):1596-1602.
19. Rodríguez M, González-Diéguez ML, Varela M, et al. Impact of alcohol abstinence on the risk of hepatocellular carcinoma in

- patients with alcohol-related liver cirrhosis. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2021;116(12):2390-2398.
20. D'Ambrosio R, Degasperis E, Anolli MP, et al. Incidence of liver- and non-liver-related outcomes in patients with HCV-cirrhosis after SVR. *J Hepatol*. 2022;76(2):302-310.
 21. Cheung MCM, Walker AJ, Hudson BE, et al. Outcomes after successful direct-acting antiviral therapy for patients with chronic hepatitis C and decompensated cirrhosis. *J Hepatol*. 2016;65(4):741-747.
 22. Jang JW, Choi JY, Kim YS, et al. Long-term effect of antiviral therapy on disease course after decompensation in patients with hepatitis B virus-related cirrhosis. *Hepatology*. 2015;61(6):1809-1820.
 23. Zhang Y, Liu X, Li S, et al. Risk of HCC decreases in HBV-related patients with cirrhosis acquired recompensation: a retrospective study based on Baveno VII criteria. *Hepatol Commun*. 2024;8(1)e0355.
 24. Lv Y, Yang Z, Liu L, et al. Early TIPS with covered stents versus standard treatment for acute variceal bleeding in patients with advanced cirrhosis: a randomised controlled trial. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2019;4(8):587-598.
 25. Nicoară-Farcău O, Han G, Rudler M, et al. Effects of early placement of transjugular portosystemic shunts in patients with high-risk

acute variceal bleeding: a meta-analysis of individual patient data. *Gastroenterology*. 2021;160(1):193-205.e10.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

How to cite this article: Sánchez J, González S, Poyatos P, et al. Recompensation after TIPS reduces the incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma and increases survival in patients with cirrhosis. *Liver Int*. 2024;44:3072-3082. doi:[10.1111/liv.16095](https://doi.org/10.1111/liv.16095)